

LEARNING POINTS FROM EXECUTING A FINAL YEAR PROJECT ENHANCED WITH DESIGN THINKING

S.M. Cheah

Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore

smcheah@sp.edu.sg

Abstract

This paper shares the experience of the author in introducing design thinking into a final year project for students studying the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE). All students from the 3-year diploma need to complete a group project as part of fulfillment of the program. More recently, the emphasis of our projects had focused on coming up with innovative products that are to be beneficial to low-income groups or community in needs - referred to as social innovation projects. The products are to utilize technology that is not overly complex, so that the people can operate or maintain it easily, make use of sustainable energy, and of course, low cost. In this project, students first used design thinking methodology to generate insights into the real needs of a community, ideate and eventually prototype possible solutions for addressing such needs. This marked a dramatic shift from past practice in project execution where students almost immediately came up with what they think is a possible way to solve the perceived problem and started working on a “solution”.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, design thinking, final year project, social innovation*

Introduction: What is Social Innovation?

Social innovation is increasingly gaining importance in the last several years, largely due to growing urgency to solve various global problems brought upon by aging population, rising cost of health care, depletion of natural resources, widening income gap, climate change, illiteracy and poverty, etc.

So, what exactly is social innovation? Mulgan et al (2007) noted that “Surprisingly little is known about social innovation compared to the vast amount of research into innovation in business and science. In an extensive survey we found no systematic overviews of the field, no major datasets or long-term analyses, and few signs of interest from the big foundations or academic research funding bodies”. A study by the Bureau of European Policy Advisors defined it as “new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or

collaborations” (BEPA, 2011). For our purpose, we adopted the “definition” given by The Center for Social Innovation at Stanford University, which stated social innovation as “the process of inventing, securing support for, and implementing novel solutions to social needs and problems” (Hartung, 2012).

DT and CDIO Framework for Projects

Engineers clearly have a role to play in helping to solve these problems. Amadei (2004) noted that: “Engineers have a collective responsibility to improve the lives of people around the world”. It is important therefore, for engineers to complement their technical and analytical capabilities with a broad understanding of “soft” issues that are non-technical. Traditionally trained engineers, however, are not educated to address the needs of the most destitute people on our planet (Sandekian et al, 2007). There is thus a need to train engineers to be more creative and actively engage them in social innovation projects.

Over the past 2 years, Singapore Polytechnic (SP) had made social innovation projects a key platform for delivering holistic education to students. An important tool for carrying out social innovation projects is design thinking. Design thinking (DT) is a popular tool used in the business world, focusing on 3 mutually supporting elements, namely that of user empathy, technical feasibility and business viability (Brown, 2009). DT is centered on innovating through the eyes of the end user and as such encourages in-the-field research that builds empathy for people, which results in deeper insights about their unmet needs (Brown, 2011).

In SP, we adapted DT for use in social innovation works and formulated own approach to projects by merging DT with the CDIO Framework which had become the basis of re-designing our engineering education (Cheah and Sale, 2012). The framework is shown in Figure 1. CDIO (www.cdio.org) is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving – Designing – Implementing – Operating (hence the acronym) real-world systems and products. For more details, see for example Cheah and Sale (2010).

Figure 1. Project Framework using DT and CDIO

From Figure 1 it can be seen that the first two stages of the DT process, namely Sense and Sensibility, and Empathy; serve to reinforce the Conceive and Design stages of the CDIO framework so that we focus on the correct problem identification, before proceeding with exploring various plausible solutions. Although represented in Figure 1 in a linear fashion, the design thinking process is best thought of as a system of three overlapping spaces of inspiration, ideation and implementation; rather than a sequence of orderly steps (Brown and Wyatt, 2010). They are not always undertaken sequentially; as a real-world project may loop back through inspiration, ideation and implementation more than once as the team refines its ideas and explore new directions.

Description of Work Done

Successfully completing a final year project (FYP) is one of the academic requirements for all students studying the 3-year Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) in order to graduate from SP. The FYP is offered as a year-long subject for all Year 3 students.

The author introduced one such DT-based FYP for his students in Academic Year 2011. The project brief requires students to come up with solution to reduce poverty among populations in developing or third-world countries. The brief also calls for the solution to be easy-to-use, easy-to-maintain, effective, using simple available technology and low cost so that it is affordable for any non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that support such initiatives, and easy enough for the local population to repair or replace the product should it be damaged or broke down. In other words, the project requires students to make use of “appropriate technologies” (a term originated by Schumacher, 1973) to address the given challenge. Appropriate technology is usually characterized as small scale, energy efficient, environmentally sound, labor-intensive, and controlled by the local community (Hazeltine and Bull, 1999).

In this FYP, the students made use of DT and went through all four stages of the CDIO process of conceiving (C), designing (D), implementing (I) and operating (O) to make a useful contribution to tackling third world poverty through an educational innovation. They identified educating children as a major way to reduce poverty, and came up with a working prototype for an educational kit that helped them learn at night; as many had to work in the field during the day.

At the C-stage, the students conducted literature surveys on illiteracy and identified poverty as a main cause; and that education is an effective way to break the poverty cycle and raise the standards of living. This is supported by interviews of SP staff with overseas community service experiences as well as personnel from a non-governmental organization (NGO) based in Vietnam. Then, using the various DT tools they had learnt in Year 2, the students came up with the idea of solar-powered education kit that would make learning fun. This is because the children would have been tired from working during the day, and now they need to attend school at night. The choice of solar power is an obvious one given that it is virtually free and definitely meets the sustainability requirement. Next, the team brainstormed for various product ideas that meet the requirements. This is followed by selecting the idea that best meet various requirements as noted in the project brief. See Figure 2. Eventually the concept of alphabet blocks was chosen to be the one to be pursued further. The concept is similar to that of “Scrabble” but larger to accommodate solar panel, batteries, switch, LED, etc.

Figure 2. (Left) Students during idea generation stage, and (Right) idea selection stage

At the D-stage, the students worked on designing the alphabet blocks. They learnt to use 3-D modeling software, operate various machines (for drilling, cutting), soldering (see Figure 3), etc to make a prototype. They bought the various components needed from local stores. In fact, they went through several rounds of prototyping, where in-between they obtained feedback from various sources: the author, SP staff with overseas community service experience (Figure 4, left), and representatives from the Vietnamese NGO. The prototypes were also tested with the teachers and children at the village in Vietnam by the NGO; but unfortunately the students were not able to join them due to clashes with their studies in Singapore as well as lack of funding for travelling.

Figure 3. Making prototype: (Left) soldering, and (Right) drilling

At the I-and-O stages, the students carried out various experiments, for example to ascertain the charging time of the solar panels, taking into account the difference in weather condition between Singapore and Vietnam, in particular in Ho Chi Minh City; as well as determining the duration that a panel will remain sufficiently well lit for use at night. They also made further refinements to the prototype, and finally met up with potential vendor to fabricate the final version (Figure 4, right). The students made a total of four different prototypes before arriving at the final design.

Figure 4. (Left) Students discussing with SP staff on improvements to a prototype made, and (Right) meeting vendor to finalize design

The final product is an alphabet block with removable alphabet plate in the front (Figure 5, left), and solar panel at the back (Figure 5, right). Magnets can be mounted at the back alongside the solar panel so that the entire block can stick onto a whiteboard, and teaching can be conducted like a game of “Scrabble” (Figure 6).

Figure 5. (Left) Final alphabet block, with removable letter plate on front side sliding into the alphabet casing, and (Right) solar panel on reverse side of the casing

Figure 6. (Left) Final alphabet blocks produced, and (Right) forming an English word

A complete set of education kit will have many such blocks and many more such plates. Using the remaining project fund available, the team managed to produce a total of six alphabet blocks and twenty alphabet plates.

They produced a materials list for the alphabet block and also suggested way to further reduce the cost so that the entire education kit is made affordable.

Considerations in Executing DT-type FYP

This is the first time that a FYP used DT and it was introduced to students from DCHE. Several factors had been considered before the author decided to proceed with this initiative. These factors are:

- (1) Deliverables: For DT-type projects it is not clear what the final outcome will be, hence, there may be reluctance on students to take up this type of projects as their FYP, especially the more ‘grade-conscious’ ones. FYP carries eight credit units which contributes significantly to a student’s GPA (Grade Point Average) score. These students are afraid that if they are unable to produce a good product, they will be given lower grades and this will affect their GPA score. The prospect of not doing well in FYP may deter some students from taking up DT-type FYPs. For this FYP, it is most fortunate that the three students had prior experience in DT, having voluntarily participated in a multi-disciplinary campus-wide project during their Year-2 of study where they were exposed to principles of DT. Hence they are quite comfortable with the project
- (2) Use of Chemical Engineering knowledge: The product prototype that the students came up with may or may not require the applications of principles in chemical engineering that they learnt. For example, the prototype may required extensive programming or may consist mostly of electrical or mechanical components integrated together. This is one of the several concerns that students had previously raised when we introduced product design into the DCHE curriculum (Cheah, 2010). To address this concern, the DCHE Course Management Team deliberated on the objectives of FYP and its intended learning outcomes, and concluded that it is the learning process that is of higher importance compared to the final product.

As it turned out in this FYP, these DCHE students came up with a product that uses more electrical engineering knowledge than chemical engineering. Not surprisingly, their knowledge of electrical circuits and soldering are somewhat limited. To this end, the author used a bit of reverse engineering by requiring them to dismantle a solar-powered torch light bought from IKEA. Through dismantling the unit and studying its working principles the students quickly mastered the necessary know-how and were able to produce their first prototype. The students are very motivated to learn new skills that were not taught to them in the DCHE curriculum.

- (3) **Timeline:** To pack all the four stages of C-D-I-O all within an academic year posed another concern. Depending of what product concept that the students come up with, it must adequately convey the intended use. It is therefore important to possess good project management skills, which comes from practice over time. For this FYP, we provided induction on key project management skills for students and closely monitored their progress in the early stages to ensure that they did not fall behind any major milestones. The author met with the students almost on a weekly basis. We also instituted a mid-year project review where students made presentations on progress made, and how they intended tackling various challenges that emerged.
- (4) **Team Composition:** DT requires divergent thinking, which works best with diverse group of people in the project team. However, in this case, the FYP students all came from the same course, i.e. DCHE. This is the constraint that we faced and it is due to the limitation in present FYP proposal system that does not permit a supervisor from including students from other disciplines. In this case, we had no choice but to proceed with these students, but fortunately they had exposure to DT, as mentioned previously, and had a basic understanding of reframing and being able to look at things from different perspectives

Challenges in Overseas Social Innovation Projects

There are several challenges that we faced in the execution of this project. Firstly, and most importantly, is the impossibility of actually conducting a user survey in the target country. There was no budget for us to fly the students to Vietnam to interview the teachers and villagers. Instead, the students had to rely on literature reviews to gain understanding of the general conditions of the target country - hence lacked the desired first-hand experience of the local conditions specific to this particular village in Vietnam. In particular, there is virtually no published information regarding a particular village of interest in this project, due to lack of in-depth study by the country's relevant organizations. However, this can be complemented to some extent through interviews with members of the NGO, to obtain a "second-hand" knowledge. We found that having an appropriate NGO is very important, as they can offer a wealth of local knowledge regarding the villages that they served.

While this has less consequence as far as technical knowledge is concerned, the real disadvantage of this approach is the lack of user empathy that needs to be developed in the students. As explained by Gallo (1989), it is "... an empathic response is one which contains both a cognitive and an affective dimension.... the term empathy [is] used in at least two ways; to mean a predominantly cognitive response, understanding how

another feels, or to mean an affective communion with the other." Hence, without physically being in the village, there is a lack of real-world context insofar as the affective domain is concerned.

In fact, the fundamental issue actually boiled down to inadequacy of the existing funding structure that does not permit both staff and students to travel together for overseas project work. The author is aware of a colleague who carried out fund-raising campaign to support her students' trip to an ASEAN country for their final year project.

Another limitation in the present funding structure is that the faculty proposing the FYP needs to provide quite detailed information on the facility needs, equipment to be used, and consumables required. However, for DT-type projects, it is not always possible for one to accurately identify what are needed for budgetary purposes. In this instance, we over-estimated ("erred on the safe side", so to speak) the funding required, and only used half the amount allocated. The unspent balance is hence channeled to another project that under-estimated its requirements so things still worked out well in the end. While the present funding structure is being reviewed, and some progress has been made to facilitate fund transfer between projects; it is not foreseeable for the next few years that improvements will be made for permit overseas travel arrangements.

In addition, there is the challenge of matching our students' timetable with the NGO's own programs. Often this is difficult to do, as this project showed. Besides working on their project on a given day, our students need to attend classes for the rest of the week. The FYP milestones do not always coincide with the NGO's travel plans. For instance, there was an occasion that the students were not able to produce a prototype in time so that the NGP can bring it to the village concerned.

Lastly, is the question of following-up after the FYP report is submitted. As far as course requirements are concerned, the students would be deemed to have met the requirements, and the students would proceed for their graduation, but such projects may not be truly "completed". Following-up can be a challenge as the remaining work to be done is not sufficiently large for the project to be continued as another FYP in the following year. This is indeed the case for this FYP.

Reflections on Key Success Factors

There are several key factors worth mentioning, which the author thinks are useful for any faculty contemplating taking up DT-type FYPs. One is the mindset of faculty supervising such project. The teaching faculty must first adopt a new mindset and be receptive to the new teaching pedagogy that in turn, requires them to first overwrite their "traditional"

approach to handling chemical engineering subjects. In other words, the teaching faculty must take care not to fall back into the “usual” way of problem solving, especially given the time pressure to maintain the project timeline, while still attempting to seek more innovative solutions.

Hence, despite being trained in DT techniques, we found that applying them in the FYP still proved challenging at the initial stage, as it ran counter to the way we were trained as engineers – to be analytical and somewhat procedural in applying an engineering solution. A useful tool for faculty is reflective practice (Schön, 1983) where a person thoughtfully evaluates his/her own experiences as he/she makes the connection between knowledge and practice.

In addition, there is a strong need for faculty teaching DT classes to develop a high level of facilitation skills which many of us, trained under the “old school” chemical engineering, did not possess. Training is necessary to support faculty in taking on a more active learning and facilitating role than the traditional “sage on the stage” approach of delivering lectures to “the masses” in a big hall.

Besides the urge to prescribe a given solution, a faculty must also show restraint from imposing his/her own ideas on the students. However, when students go well off-course faculty need to tactfully steer them back without being seen as dictating what or how to solve the problem. As such, building rapport with the students at an early stage is crucial. Facilitation is thus especially important during the initial stages, where students tend to spend more time than allocated on a given task (e.g. interview, brainstorming or ideation). Also, facilitation is often very situational, which means that a faculty must constantly be on the alert and detect any sign of uneasiness among students.

Another important point is the readiness of faculty to admit that, at times, we do not have all the answers. To this end, we felt that besides good “people skills”, another important requirement for good facilitation is that a faculty must read widely and be knowledgeable in many diverse fields, though not necessary as an expert. It is the breadth of knowledge that matters more than the depth, especially on various social issues.

Moving Ahead

For DT-type FYPs to be successfully executed, engineering students need to think more creatively, in order to tackle various global issues. In our context, the interpretation of creativity by Coyne (1997) is most apt: “Thinking creatively involves perceiving situations from new perspectives and generating novel ideas for solving complex problems.” Furthermore, the work of Swann and Birke (2005) positively linked creativity and design to innovation. O’Rafferty et al (2009) also argued that creativity is a pre-requisite for innovation

and design. Stouffer et al (2004) made the case that fostering creativity knowledge, skills and attitudes is vital for the future of engineering and engineering education, further noting that “without training in the fundamentals of creativity, it is little wonder that so few engineers are viewed as creative professionals”.

Felder (1987) for example, had long ago advocated the need to train engineers to be more creative. He proposed that faculty provide more opportunities for students to practice these skills, “so that these thinking and problem-solving skills come to be thought of as routinely applied tools of the engineers’ trade”. Kazerounian and Foley (2007) asserted that creativity is possible for engineering students and reported, from their research, that most engineering students felt they presently lack creativity in their educational experience. Santamarina and Akhondi (2003) noted that education and proper design of the learning environment can help develop and maintain creative abilities among students. Our own experience with DT-infused projects indicated that given the right environment and supported by timely encouragement, our students can be more creative and are able to come up new ideas and better solutions.

Deciding that mastering the tools of DT is important, the DCHE Course Management Team had integrated DT teaching into its curriculum, namely for the Year 1 module *Introduction to Chemical Product Design (ICPD)*. The integration framework is shown in Figure 7, where the module served to prepare students early in their course of study to come up with innovative product concepts which ideally will be further developed and refined in Year 2 in the module *Product Design and Development*, and eventually translated into viable prototype or pilot plant in Year 3 as FYP.

Figure 7. Integration of Design Thinking into Chemical Product Design

The module was first rolled out in Semester 2 of Academic Year 2011. From the onset our emphasis is on students coming up with chemical product ideas using appropriate technologies. Sandekian et al (2007) noted that because appropriate technology is often perceived as “low tech” and unimportant, it is not usually addressed in engineering education or university research. However, we felt that appropriate technologies are well suited for our needs at the diploma-level; as our students need not master a very high level of technical competencies at this level of study. What is more important for students is that they have the opportunity

to apply what they learn in real life contexts which results in more meaningful learning, enhanced confidence in their own abilities to contribute, and more importantly, from an educational perspective, sustain interest in chemical engineering. Lastly, we also need to develop suitable rubrics for guiding assessment of various components in the DT process.

Conclusions

The introduction of DT into FYP can lead to better ideation and hence a better solution that truly meets the requirements of targeted end users. Successful faculty project supervision requires a higher level of facilitation skills than in the more advisory role expected of FYP supervisor per se. There are still significant challenges – some structural and administrative in nature – that need to be overcome if the execution of such projects is to come to fruition in terms of the lofty aim of improving conditions in third world/developing countries. However, the work presented in this paper will hopefully enhance our understanding of the complex pedagogic and ergonomic issues that are crucial to making such projects both highly worthwhile learning experiences for our students and making significant contributions to community – even global need.

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